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Responsible Leadership as a Boundary Condition for Green HRM and Sustainable Performance: Evidence from Pakistan's Service SMEs

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for corporate sustainability has increased scholarly and managerial interest in the organizational factors that improve sustainable performance. Among these factors, Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM) has emerged as an important internal mechanism for embedding environmental responsibility into employee management systems. This study examines the role of responsible leadership as a boundary condition in the relationship between Green HRM and sustainable performance in Pakistan's service-sector small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). A quantitative research design was employed using survey data collected from 393 respondents working in service SMEs in Pakistan. Data were analyzed through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test direct and moderating relationships. The findings reveal that Green HRM has a significant positive effect on sustainable performance. In contrast, responsible leadership does not exert a significant direct effect on sustainable performance. However, the interaction effect between Green HRM and responsible leadership is positive and significant, confirming that leadership enhances the effectiveness of environmental HR systems. The study contributes to the literature by extending Green HRM research beyond direct-effect models and introducing a contingency perspective. Practically, the findings suggest that SMEs should combine environmental HR initiatives with responsible leadership development to achieve stronger economic, environmental, and social outcomes.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management; Responsible Leadership; Sustainable Performance; Stakeholder Theory; SMEs; Pakistan; Sustainability Management;

Introduction

Sustainability is the new strategic focus of modern organizations. Companies are now more and more anticipated to create economic value and, at the same time, minimize environmental damage and make a positive impact on society. This wider

expectation has changed the definition of organizational success from the limits of short-term profitability to long-term sustainable performance. Consequently, under mounting regulatory, customer, investor, employee, and community pressure, firms are increasingly obliged to integrate the concept of sustainability into their internal processes and management approaches (Afum et al., 2020; Zaharia and Zaharia, 2021).

Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM) is one of the most important internal processes by which organizations work towards sustainability. Green HRM is a concept that encompasses how human resource policies and practices are aligned with environmental goals by performing green recruitment, environmental training, rewards based on sustainability, employee participation, and encouragement of ecological activities by managers (Bombiak, 2019; Zaid et al., 2018). Green HRM does not view sustainability as a department function in isolation but rather as a component in the employee lifecycle and organizational culture. These practices can help firms promote pro-environmental behavior, enhance the commitment of employees, and enhance sustainability performance.

Though the existing body of research tends to confirm the positive relationship between Green HRM and organizational sustainability, the results are not that consistent. A lot of companies follow the environmental HR policies; however, without achieving significant performance gains. Green HRM initiatives are, in other instances, symbolic, disjointed or poorly realized. In others, there are formal policies, but there is little strategic direction, little managerial support, or reinforcement to the employees. Such mixed results imply that there might not be equal effectiveness of Green HRM in every organizational context. Its success can be contingent on situational factors that define the extent to which HR practices are proactively implemented in organizational behavior and quantifiable outcomes.

Another contextual condition critical yet under-researched is that of leadership. Formal expectations are defined by HR systems, but leaders determine the interpretation, prioritization, and implementation of those expectations in the day-to-day organizational life. Employees tend to judge the sustainability initiatives based on the seriousness of the initiatives by the managers, rather than the policies.

Green HRM practices are bound to be more legitimate and yield results when leaders overtly endorse environmental objectives, allocate, reward, and integrate stakeholder interests in the decision-making process. On the contrary, in the case of a weak leadership commitment, HR initiatives can be procedural and ineffective.

The idea of responsible leadership contributes particularly in this respect. Responsible leadership focuses on ethical decision-making, stakeholder involvement, long-term orientation, and social and environmental responsibility (Voegtlin, 2016; Waldman et al., 2006). In contrast to the strictly performance-based leadership models, responsible leadership directly links the managerial power with sustainability and value creation to stakeholders. These leaders will have a higher probability of supporting environmental programs, leading by example, and aligning the organizational mechanisms with sustainability objectives. Thus, the effectiveness of Green HRM in the generation of sustainable performance can be enhanced by responsible leadership.

This is of great concern in new economies like Pakistan. Developing context organizations tend to have institutional limitations, inadequate enforcement of regulations, deficient resources, and changing sustainability consciousness. Formal HR systems might not be enough to bring change in such environments. Leadership commitment can turn out to be a deciding factor that balances out structural flaws and garners internal enthusiasm for sustainability efforts. This is particularly applicable to small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) that prevail in the Pakistani service sector and often do not have a highly formalized system but instead depend on the discretion of managers (Koirala, 2019; Chughtai et al., 2024).

The service sector of Pakistan is a significant contributor to both GDP and employment of the country; however, it is relatively underinvestigated in sustainability research. Service firms also tend to produce less apparent environmental impact, relative to manufacturing industries, leading to a less strategic focus on sustainability efforts. Nevertheless, service organizations use energy, create waste, affect customer behavior, and impact sustainable consumption patterns. Their reliance on people-based processes also implies that the HR systems and leadership behaviour can be especially effective in defining the sustainability

results.

Using the Stakeholder Theory, the paper will present its thesis that the best sustainable performance of firms is attained when the internal management systems are congruent with the leadership that is grounded on stakeholders. Green HRM offers the official framework of environmental responsibility, whereas responsible leadership sets the behavioral and strategic frameworks within which those frameworks can work. Based on this, this paper investigates the question of whether responsible leadership enhances the association between Green HRM practices and sustainable performance within the service-sector SMEs in Pakistan.

Problem Statement

Although there is an increasing organizational interest in Green HRM, most companies do not translate environmental HR practices into valuable, sustainable performance results. Previous studies have mostly focused on the direct impacts of Green HRM, in many cases, thinking that formal HR practices can deliver sustainability outcomes automatically. Nevertheless, there is still a lack of evidence, especially in developing economies where institutional backing and organizational capacities are not evenly dispersed.

One of the greatest weaknesses of previous studies is that they have not paid enough attention to the contextual leadership conditions that dictate whether or not Green HRM practices are successfully applied. Formal HR systems can be indicators of environmental priorities, though not with supportive leadership; they can be symbolic, loosely applied, and unrelated to operational decision-making. Despite the fact that responsible leadership has been identified as applicable to sustainability, there is a scarcity of empirical research that has focused on its moderating effect on the relationship between Green HRM and performance, particularly in the SMEs of the service sector in Pakistan.

As a result, the issue of whether responsible leadership is a boundary that enhances the performance of Green HRM practices to attain sustainable performance requires exploration.

This research aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To examine the effect of Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM)

practices on sustainable performance in Pakistan's service-sector SMEs.

- To assess the influence of responsible leadership on sustainable performance.
- To investigate whether responsible leadership moderates the relationship between Green HRM practices and sustainable performance.
- To provide contextual evidence on leadership-driven sustainability in Pakistan's service economy.

Literature Review

2.1 Green Human Resource Management and Sustainable Performance

Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM) has become a strategic reaction towards the increase in demand towards sustainability of organizations. It can be defined as the incorporation of environmental issues in the mainstream HR activities like recruitment, training, performance appraisal, rewards, and participation of employees. With the help of these practices, organizations aim at aligning the behavior of the workforce with the ecological goals and the introduction of sustainability into the daily routines (Bombiak, 2019; Renwick et al., 2016).

Green HRM is relevant because it can have an impact on the human aspect of sustainability. Employees not being aware, motivated, or able to support environmental strategies can lead to failure. HR systems cope with this issue by molding competencies, incentives, and behavioral standards. Green recruitment assists in recruiting applicants whose values match with environmental responsibility. Green training imparts technical and behavior skills needed to work efficiently in an eco-friendly manner. Green rewards support a performance related to sustainability, and participation systems promote employee engagement in resolving environmental issues.

These processes are strongly related to sustainable performance, which is usually considered as the capacity of the organization to produce positive results in economic, environmental, and social areas. Sustainability can enhance productivity, efficiency and reputation, economically. It minimizes waste, emissions and consumption of resources in the environment. It raises the well-being of employees, trust among stakeholders, and ethical legitimacy socially (Afum et al., 2020; Zaharia and Zaharia,

2021).

Empirical research often indicates that there are positive relationships between Green HRM and sustainability outcomes. Companies that have more robust environmental HR practices tend to be more eco-performing, have higher employee engagement, and more stable sustainability-wise behavior (Saeed et al., 2019; Yong et al., 2020). But the strength of this relationship is not always constant. Other organizations have put funds into Green HRM and have not achieved significant gains in performance, implying that formal HR systems might be inadequate. It shows that it is necessary to study contextual circumstances that define when Green HRM is more efficient.

2.2 Responsible Leadership and Organizational Sustainability

Leadership is one of the key elements in making organizational systems a practice. Although HR policies establish structures and expectations, leaders are the ones who make the difference between them being taken seriously, continuously applied and prioritized strategically. Managerial actions are often construed by the employees as organizational priorities, instead of written policy documents. Consequently, the effect of formal HR systems can be increased or diminished through the leadership behavior (Egri and Herman, 2000).

In the context of sustainability, responsible leadership is especially applicable. It is the leadership orientation of ethical behavior, engagement with stakeholders, accountability, long-term orientation, and being sensitive to the social and environmental implications of the decisions (Voegtlin, 2016; Waldman et al., 2006). Accountable leaders are not preoccupied with internal efficiencies or short-run financial performance; accountable leaders are balancing a variety of stakeholder interests and are thinking of sustainable value creation.

This type of leadership can directly help in achieving sustainable performance in a number of ways. To start with, accountable leaders invest in environmental and social priorities. Second, they establish sustainability initiatives through the establishment of strategic commitment. Third, they set a good example; they exemplify responsible behavior, and this constructs attitudes and norms of employees. Fourth, they promote cross-functional teamwork and making long-term

decisions, which are vital to sustainability implementation (Afsar et al., 2020).

The previous studies associate responsible leadership with more positive ethical climates, stakeholder trust, employee commitment, and sustainability outcomes (Ahmad et al., 2021; Darvishmotevali and Altinay, 2022). Leadership commitment is still more significant in emerging markets where institutions might be weaker, and, instead of a formal governance system, managerial discretion is more likely to prevail (Khan et al., 2024).

2.3 Why Responsible Leadership Should Strengthen Green HRM Effects

Despite the fact that Green HRM offers formal environmental management mechanisms, its success hinges on the quality of implementation. HR systems can be paper-based, and in the absence of leadership, they will just be symbolic or compliance-oriented (Renwick et al., 2016; Bombiak, 2019). Green HRM can be empowered by responsible leadership in a number of significant aspects.

To begin with, leaders bring about strategic alignment. Green HRM practices are integrated into overall organizational objectives as opposed to a stand-alone HR initiative when managers are able to communicate sustainability priorities regularly. Second, leaders distribute both attention and resources. When the leadership is involved, training programs, reward systems, and participation platforms will be more effective. Third, leaders affirm credibility. When they see leaders themselves exhibiting a sense of environmental responsibility, workers tend to become more susceptible to green behaviors. Fourth, leaders decrease resistance to change by justifying sustainability-seeking changes in practices and expectations (Robertson and Barling, 2013; Luu, 2019).

This reasoning implies that there could be an interaction effect, but not a direct effect. Green HRM can enhance sustainable performance, although the size of the effect ought to be greater with high responsible leadership and less with low responsible leadership. In this aspect, leadership is a boundary condition that defines the effectiveness of environmental HR systems in generating results (Afsar et al., 2020; Darvishmotevali and Altinay, 2022; Ahmad et al., 2021).

This is particularly applicable to SMEs. Smaller companies tend to have more owner-managers and top managers than formal bureaucracies. In turn, the leadership

behavior can impact the meaningful implementation of Green HRM initiatives more (Koirala, 2019).

Research Gap

Although there is an increasing focus on Green HRM and sustainability, there are still three significant gaps. To begin with, much of the literature that currently exists has focused on direct associations between the Green HRM and performance, providing a limited insight into the situational circumstances in which the associations will be stronger or weaker. This leaves unanswered the question as to when Green HRM is most effective.

Second, responsible leadership is a research topic in ethics and stakeholder management studies, yet its mediating impact on Green HRM results has not been developed. There is a paucity of literature where leadership and HR sustainability systems are incorporated into a single empirical framework.

Third, little evidence exists in developing economies, especially in service-sector SMEs. The majority of the previous research is based on big companies or manufacturing settings of developed markets. The results are unlikely to be directly applicable to the service economy of Pakistan, where greater levels of managerial discretion, resource limitations, and informality exist.

This paper fills these gaps by exploring responsible leadership as a boundary condition in the correlation between Green HRM and sustainable performance in the service-sector SMEs in Pakistan.

Theoretical Foundation

This paper is based on Stakeholder Theory. Stakeholder Theory states that organizations can generate long-term value by attentively responding to the demands of various stakeholder groups instead of concentrating on only shareholders. These stakeholders are employees, customers, communities, regulators, suppliers and society in general.

Green HRM embodies this rationale as it incorporates environmental responsibility into employee management systems. It is an indication of dedication towards internal and external stakeholders who are increasingly demanding responsible business practice. Nevertheless, formal systems by themselves might not meet the

expectations of the stakeholders without the active support and legitimization of the organizational leaders.

Responsible leadership is a behavioral level operationalization of stakeholder-oriented management. These leaders are more aware and conscious of general responsibilities, reconcile conflicting interests and make long-term social and environmental decisions. Thus, responsible leadership should be coupled with Green HRM, and organizations should be in a better position to realize sustainable performance.

Stakeholder Theory thus provides a clear explanation for the proposed moderation model: Green HRM creates sustainability-oriented systems, responsible leadership strengthens stakeholder-responsive implementation, and together they enhance sustainable performance. Based on the above literature and theoretical reasoning, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1: Green Human Resource Management practices positively influence sustainable performance.

H2: Responsible leadership positively influences sustainable performance.

H3: Responsible leadership positively moderates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management practices and sustainable performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Methodology

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This study employed positivism and deductive research philosophy to empirically establish the proposed relationships between Green HRM and responsible leadership with sustainable performance. A quantitative design was considered appropriate because the aim of the research was to test the hypothesized relationships using statistical tests and generalizable data. The research model was founded on the direct effects and the moderating effects; thus, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) survey method is an appropriate analysis tool.

The target population was employees and managers of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the service industry in Pakistan. This background was selected because the human resource, managerial behaviour and organisation routine are most often important in service companies, hence the reason behind seeking the research on leadership and HR-based sustainability practices. Moreover, the Pakistani economy heavily involves SMEs, which are more likely to be less formal, which, again, increases the significance of the impact of leadership.

Data were collected using the structured questionnaire according to the measurement scales that were validated in the literature. The survey instrument included the Green HRM practices, responsible leadership and sustainable performance. The responses were recorded on a five-point Likert scale, where 1 = strongly disagree, and 5 strongly agree. The use of homogeneous scales helped to enhance the content validity and homogeneity of constructs.

Unusable responses were 393 (the final dataset was made of the usable ones). It was a large enough sample size to provide SEM analysis and larger than the generally accepted sample size to test the effects of interaction in latent-variable models. They were of different levels of management, education and different types of experience, thereby improving the diversity and representativeness of the respondents.

Data analysis was performed in two stages with the help of Structural Equation Modeling. Factor loadings, internal consistency reliability and convergent and discriminant validity were the first measurement models used to assess the measurement model. Second, the structural model was tested to test the hypothesized direct and moderating relationships. The moderation effect was also examined using interaction terms between the Green HRM dimensions and the

responsible leadership to determine whether leadership augmented the Green HRM effect on sustainable performance. Strong results were also determined by comparing model fit statistics, tests of collinearity, explanatory power (R^2) and effect sizes (f^2).

The study was conducted in an ethical manner. The research was done on a voluntary basis, and the respondents were informed about the academic purpose of the study and the secrecy of their personal answers. No personal data was published, and the data were used only in the research.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Category	N	%
Gender	Male	251	63.9
	Female	142	36.1
Age	Under 20	9	2.3
	21–30	37	9.4
	31–40	115	29.3
	41–50	136	34.6
	51–60	78	19.8
	Over 60	18	4.6
Education	High School	4	1.0
	Bachelor’s Degree	33	8.4

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Variable	Category	N	%
	Master's Degree	201	51.1
	PhD	129	32.8
	Other	26	6.6
Experience	Less than 1 year	10	2.5
	1–5 years	36	9.2
	6–10 years	187	47.6
	11–15 years	127	32.3
	Over 15 years	33	8.4
Designation	Lower-level management	85	21.6
	Middle-level management	198	50.4
	Upper-level management	110	28.0

The findings indicate that the sample consisted mostly of men (63.9%). The majority of the participants were aged 31 to 50 years, suggesting a mature and work-experienced workforce. The sample in terms of education was very qualified, with most of them having a master's degree or a PhD. Regarding organization role, more than three-fourths of the respondents were in middle and upper-level management, and the sample was appropriate to assess leadership, HR systems and sustainability practices.

Table 2: Factor Loadings

Construct	Loading Range
Green Compensation & Reward (GCR)	0.798 – 0.869

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Construct	Loading Range
Green Employee Empowerment (GEEP)	0.867 – 0.920
Green Manager Involvement (GMI)	0.751 – 0.826
Green Selection & Recruitment (GSR)	0.792 – 0.879
Green Training & Development (GTD)	0.803 – 0.879
Responsible Leadership (LR)	0.637 – 0.812
Sustainable Performance (SP)	0.719 – 0.795

All the indicators were above the minimum acceptable value of 0.60, with the majority being above 0.70. This ensures a good level of indicator reliability and indicates that the items observed were sufficient to measure their intended constructs.

Table 3: Reliability and Convergent Validity

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
GCR	0.798	0.881	0.712
GEEP	0.751	0.888	0.799
GMI	0.886	0.912	0.635
GSR	0.802	0.882	0.715
GTD	0.808	0.885	0.720
LR	0.969	0.967	0.548
SP	0.921	0.934	0.585

The findings show that there is high internal consistency since all the Cronbach alpha and composite reliability coefficients obtained were greater than 0.70. Similarly, all AVE values are greater than 0.50, which proves convergent validity. Responsible Leadership was very high in reliability, and this indicates a high degree of consistency in the indicators used.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

Highest HTMT Value	Interpretation
0.361	Acceptable

All HTMT values were found to be below the recommended cut-off, which indicated that the constructs were empirically independent of each other. This helps to uphold the discriminant validity of the model.

Table 5: Collinearity Statistics

Path	VIF
LR → SP	1.040
LR × GCR → SP	1.066
LR × GEEP → SP	1.097
LR × GMI → SP	1.137
LR × GTD → SP	1.129
LR × GI → SP	1.007

VIF all values were significantly lower than the mark of 5.0, which means that there was no problem of multicollinearity. Predictor variables were added as independent variables to the structural model.

Table 6: Model Fit Indices

Index	Value
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Index	Value
SRMR	0.045
NFI	0.836

The SRMR of 0.045 indicates a good fit of the model since it is less than the recommended value of 0.08. Though the NFI value was a little less than 0.90, it is acceptable in PLS-SEM models of medium complexity.

Table 7: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Endogenous Variable	R²	Adjusted R²
Sustainable Performance	0.690	0.687

The model explained 69.0% of the variation in Sustainable Performance, which is a strong explanatory power. This implies that the ability of Green HRM and Responsible Leadership to predict sustainability outcomes significantly is achieved collectively.

Table 8: Direct Effects

Hypothesis	Path	β	t	p	Decision
H1	Green HRM → Sustainable Performance	0.284	7.791	0.000	Supported
H2	Responsible Leadership → Sustainable Performance	0.000	0.214	0.831	Not Supported

According to the findings, Green HRM positively affects Sustainable Performance ($\beta = 0.284, p < 0.001$), and this has a positive and statistically significant impact on the outcome, which supports H1. It proves that companies that have more robust green HR attain a higher level of sustainability. Nonetheless, the correlation between Responsible Leadership and Sustainable Performance was not statistically significant

($\beta = 0.000$, $p = 0.831$). Thus, H2 is not justified.

Table 9: Moderation Effect

Hypothesis	Path	β	t	p	Decision
H3	Green HRM × Responsible Leadership → Sustainable Performance	0.262*	3.678	0.000	Supported

The moderation analysis shows that Responsible Leadership plays a significant role in strengthening the positive relationship between Green HRM and Sustainable Performance. H3 was supported as the interaction effect was statistically significant ($= 0.262$, $p < 0.001$). This implies that when organizations are managed by accountable, stakeholder-oriented and long-term responsible managers, the sustainability results of Green HRM practices are more effective. The evidence of the overall moderation effect was the strongest interaction estimate based on the Green HRM dimensions.

Table 10: Additional Interaction Diagnostics

Green HRM Dimension × Responsible Leadership	β	t	p
Training & Development	0.262	3.678	0.000
Manager Involvement	0.238	3.450	0.001
Employee Empowerment	0.206	3.291	0.001
Compensation & Reward	0.182	2.534	0.011

In order to get a clearer picture of the general moderation outcome, there were more interaction estimates studied based on dimensions of Green HRM. Green Training and Development had the greatest strengthening effect as compared to managerial involvement and employee empowerment. This implies that leadership is particularly significant in the context where sustainability relies on learning, capacity building and employee involvement.

Summary of Findings

On the whole, the results indicate that Green HRM plays a significant role in enhancing Sustainable Performance, but Responsible Leadership does not have a direct influence on sustainability. Nevertheless, leadership has a significant contingent role, reinforcing the effectiveness of Green HRM practices. Green Training and Development was the strongest moderating effect, then there was managerial involvement and employee empowerment. These findings lead to the conclusion that leadership is a boundary condition that is used to decide when Green HRM can be more effective in creating sustainability performance.

Discussion

The main purpose of the study was to focus on the idea of whether responsible leadership is a boundary condition in the association between the Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM) and sustainable performance in the service-sector SMEs of Pakistan. The results provide a more situational interpretation of sustainability management by demonstrating that formal environmental HR systems are important, but they operate significantly based on leadership context. Contrary to the linear models, which presuppose that the outcomes of the HR practices are automatic, the findings suggest that the sustainability performance is more pronounced in the case of the reinforcement of Green HRM by the responsible leadership behavior.

The initial significant discovery is that Green HRM has a positive and significant impact on sustainable performance. This implies that environmental goals are more likely to be achieved when implicated in recruitment systems, training programs, reward systems, participation systems, as well as managerial habits. Green HRM seems to be an internal governance tool that contributes to harmonizing employee behavior with sustainability at large. These practices enable firms to minimize behavioral resistance, enhance environmental consciousness, promote resource-conscious practices, and entrench sustainability expectations throughout the workforce. This result is aligned with the accumulating literature stating that Green HRM leads to improved environmental performance, employee commitment, eco-efficiency, and long-term organizational performance (Tang et al., 2018; Saeed et al.,

2019; Amrutha and Geetha, 2020).

The Green HRM effect is especially important in terms of the SME environment. Smaller companies do not always have advanced environmental technologies or a department of sustainability or official compliance systems. When this happens, people-management systems are among the most available strategic tools that can be used by the management. Instead of having to invest heavily in technological transformation, SMEs can enhance sustainability by influencing the capabilities, values, and discretionary behavior of their employees. This is in line with arguments that HR systems are particularly useful in resource-constrained organizations in which competitive advantage relies more on human and relational capital than on scale economies or capital intensity (Koirala, 2019).

The second significant result is that responsible leadership did not have any statistically significant direct impact on sustainable performance. This might seem to be incompatible with the research that associates leadership with ethical climate, stakeholder trust and sustainability outcomes. Nevertheless, the finding is theoretically significant in that it would indicate that leadership might not generate quantifiable sustainability effects alone. Leadership values and communication, as well as ethical orientation, are great, yet they might need underpinning organizational systems before they can be converted into working outcomes. That is, leadership in itself can be used to indicate intent without the need to alter routines, incentives or employee behavior on a large scale. This meaning is consistent with contingency schools of thought that assert that the effectiveness of leadership is based on structural alignment and implementation processes as opposed to the personality or values (Voegtlin et al., 2012).

This insignificant direct effect is also the reason why mixed results have been occasionally reported in the past leadership research. Sustainability results are multidimensional, and in most cases cumulative; they develop over time through policies, systems, innovation processes and employee actions. A leadership style can thus be influential in an indirect manner, by modifying climate, fortifying systems, and distributing resources without having a large standalone coefficient in structural models. Leadership commitment can be required but not adequate in SMEs, where

managers are often financially constrained, have short planning horizons, and operational pressures; unless it is included within formal management practices. In line with this, the current results contribute to the literature by suggesting that responsible leadership is not to be regarded as an independent predictor, but rather as an enabling factor enhancing sustainability-focused systems returns (Afsar et al., 2020; Luu, 2019; Darvishmotevali and Altinay, 2022).

The findings of the study are the most significant because of the moderation findings. The positive correlation between Green HRM and sustainable performance was greatly enhanced by responsible leadership. This validates that the usefulness of environmental HR systems depends on the leadership behavior. The more leaders are accountable, sensitive to the stakeholders, long-term oriented, and obviously committed to sustainability, the more credible, coherent, and behaviorally effective Green HRM practices are. When they are upheld by the leadership, employees are also more likely to take green recruitment standards seriously, engage in environmental training, react to rewards related to sustainability, and engage in voluntary green activities.

The effect of interaction here is highly in line with Stakeholder Theory. Green HRM is an official organizational reaction to the demands of stakeholders, as it incorporates green responsibility into HR design. This architecture is complemented by responsible leadership that converts the values of the stakeholders into daily choices and social indicators. Systems and leadership together form more powerful stakeholder-responsive organizations. The results thus indicate that sustainability cannot be conceptualized as either the product of single practices, but rather as the outcome of alignment between formal systems and managerial practices (Schaltegger, 2019; Voegtlin, 2016).

Behavioral implications of the stronger performance of the moderation pathway are also possible. Employees tend to test the authenticity of organizations through observation of whether leaders are walking the talk. When there are Green HRM policies, but leaders are not concerned about the environment, employees can sense inconsistency and lessen engagement. On the other hand, psychological trust and normative commitment are enhanced when the HR messages are congruent with

leadership behavior. This uniformity is probably the reason behind the amplified Green HRM effectiveness attributed to responsible leadership in the current research. This finding is consistent with social learning and signaling views, which hold that workers deduce what is acceptable by watching how the managers behave and the organizational signals (Robertson and Barling, 2013).

Further results revealed that the greatest effects of interaction manifested themselves around training and development, managerial involvement, and employee empowerment. This trend is logically reasonable. These practices need to be reinforced at the managerial level to bring them to fruition. Leaders who devote time, resources, and follow-up resources make training programs more effective. Empowerment programs are effective when the leaders are sincere in sharing discretion, and not just talk symbolically of participation. When top leaders authorize sustainability as a strategic priority, then the involvement of managers becomes more important. Conversely, additional administrative practices like reward systems might be less dependent on daily leadership reinforcement as formal criteria are in place. This subtle trend reflects the results of earlier research that revealed that participative and developmental HR practices are particularly prone to managerial support and leadership climate (Kim et al., 2019; De Prins et al., 2020).

The results are especially applicable in the context of the institutions in Pakistan. In most of the emerging economies, sustainability rules are dynamic, enforcement ability can be unequal, and pressures of the stakeholders across sectors vary. In this case, external institutional gaps can be filled by internal leadership commitment. Action towards sustainability can be mobilized by responsible leaders even when market or regulatory incentives are feeble. This renders leadership an important voluntary device of governance in situations whereby formal external forces have yet to mature. The investigation thus provides context-specific findings that the efficacy of Green HRM can be more or less based on the institutional maturity and managerial focus (Khan et al., 2024; Chughtai et al., 2024).

In a larger strategic approach, the findings point to the fact that sustainability performance can not be created by single actions. Aristocracy of the HR systems can turn to being merely ritual, and the aristocracy of leadership to rhetorical one. When

organizations integrate structured people-management practices and responsible managerial behaviors, competitive and sustainable advantage seems to come into being. This is an addition to the ability-based perspectives of the firm by implying that organizational capabilities are not just based on the resources and routines, but also on the leadership processes that put resources into action in the actual operating conditions.

On balance, the above discussion has shown that Green HRM is a useful mechanism of sustainable performance, yet it has a significantly greater influence in responsible leadership. The results take the literature beyond direct-effect assumptions and towards a more integrated account, where leadership dictates when sustainability-oriented HR systems can lead to actual organizational deliverables.

Implications and Contributions

The research has both theoretical and practical implications in that it shows that the success of Green HRM is based on the context of leadership. The results are an extension of the Stakeholder Theory in that it demonstrates that sustainability results come about when organizational systems (Green HRM) are harmonized with stakeholder-oriented leadership (responsible leadership). It turns the emphasis on direct-effect models to a contingency viewpoint, and emphasizes that the HR practices cannot be relied on without an accompanying leadership behavior to maintain the same.

In practical terms, the findings have indicated that organisations need to incorporate the concepts of Green HRM and active leadership support as opposed to viewing them as two different initiatives. Managers need to be seen to support sustainability, invest resources, and make sure that there is a consistent HR practice implementation. The high effect of interaction in training means that training supported by the leadership is of particular importance. In the case of SMEs, where formal systems are usually small, leadership behavior can play a significant role in facilitating the transfer of HR policies into tangible sustainability results. The policymakers ought to encourage the adoption of Green HRM and leadership development as a way of enhancing sustainability practices.

Limitations and Future Research.

There are a number of limitations to this study. First, the cross-sectional design restricts the interpretation as it is causal and future research needs to employ longitudinal data to represent dynamic effects. Second, self-reported measures can also be subject to bias; subsequent research ought to include multi-source or objective performance measures. Third, the emphasis on service-sector SMEs in Pakistan restricts the generalizability; the model should be tested in other industries, company sizes and nations in future studies.

Other moderators that can be examined in future research include organizational culture, regulatory pressure or technological capability. Additionally, exploring other mediating variables (e.g., employee green behavior or innovation) would allow us to gain a better understanding of how Green HRM can be translated into performance.

Conclusion

This paper has discussed how responsible leadership can help to influence the effectiveness of Green HRM in relation to sustainable performance. The results affirm that Green HRM positively impacts sustainability results, and responsible leadership complements this connection and does not have a direct impact on performance.

The findings point to the fact that sustainability does not happen due to policies but is attained by aligning systems and leadership behavior. Companies that integrate organized HR practices and responsible leadership are in a better position to attain sustained performance in the long term, especially in the resource-limited SME environment.

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